

Fig. 1. Data movement in our algorithms, illustrated for $p = 8$ processors and replication factor $c = 2$. Within each layer, submatrices shown in yellow are cyclically shifted from processor to processor (propagation) in the direction indicated by single-headed blue arrows. Submatrices in orange are replicated across layers and participate in reduce-scatter / all-gather operations before or after each propagation phase (depending on the particular algorithm). Submatrices in red remain stationary on each processor. Black numbered circles denote the processor that owns a submatrix at the beginning of each algorithm (note the initial skew for the 2.5D algorithms).